

mo*c Transforming as Time in Special Relativity and the Notion of E,p and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April, 29, 2025

In previous notes, we have tried to derive the Lorentz transformation as a strictly spacetime transformation acting on x and t variables. In fact, we have argued that one may transform intervals of x and t in a rest frame for a co-ordinate axes even for the case of a photon. In other notes, we argued that the same transformation applies to the variables p (momentum) and E (energy), with p being proportional to the Newtonian concept $p=mo v$. In fact, we argued that one may try to apply the Lorentz transformation to mo because of the a priori knowledge of $p=mov$.

Here we assume no knowledge of $p=mo*v$ (nonrelativistic) and only knowledge of $x'=vt'$. As a result, the Lorentz is strictly a spacetime transformation. We thus argue that if one wishes to use $mo*A/c$, where A is some constant, in a transformation, then given that mo exists in the rest frame, moA must have the interpretation of ct . We suggest that this may imply that mo is proportional to the time required to assemble mo , one Δmo at a time. In other words, this is like a frozen time interval which allows one to use $mo*A$ in a Lorentz transformation. We argue that such an interpretation applies to $mo*c$ or E/c and not E . pc then becomes a length interval such that $p*c/(mo*c) = v$, just like $x'/t'=v$. If one wishes to switch to p, E variables for physical reasons (Newtonian mechanics), then the equation: $1/E cc/v= 1/p$ applies and one finds $constant/E$ and $constant/p$ time and spatial intervals. Thus, $mo*c$ is used as a time interval in the first place to justify using the Lorentz transformation, but a change to $E=mo*cc$ leads to $constant/E$ representing a different time interval and $constant/p$ a different spatial one, namely ones associated with interactions, we suggest and free particle quantum mechanics. These physical variables E and p are, however, not the one which justify the use of the Lorentz invariant.

Lorentz Transformation Strictly as a Spatial Transformation

We have argued in previous notes that the Lorentz transformation is strictly a spacetime transformation. The point $x=0, bt=0$ (b is a constant with velocity units) transforms to $x'=0, bt'=0$ as seen in a frame moving with $-v$. If one has another point in a rest frame of a co-ordinate axes, namely $x=0, t$ then this point has evolved from $(x=0, t=0)$, but in the moving frame, the evolution would be: $x'=vt', t'$. One must assume a different t' so that:

$$Xx- ctct = x'x' - ct'tct' \quad ((1))$$

This may be shown to lead to the Lorentz transformation:

$$\begin{aligned} &| g(v/b) \quad v/b \quad g(v/b) | \quad ((2)) \\ &| v/b \quad g(v/b) \quad g(v/b) \quad | \end{aligned}$$

Applying ((2)) to a photon transformation: $x/t=c$ and $x'/t' =c$ leads to $c=b$. Note: $g(v/c) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$.

As a result, the Lorentz transformation is a spacetime one. In previous notes, we have argued for applying it to m_0 (rest mass), on the basis of the existence of the Newtonian equation:

$$p = m_0 \cdot v = \text{momentum} \quad ((3))$$

Here we assume that we do not know that momentum exists. This then forces one to try to transform m_0 as being proportional to a time.

Transforming $m_0 \cdot A/c$ as a Time under a Lorentz Transformation

In a rest frame for a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$, time t is a running variable. Given that x is fixed at say $x=0$, one may ask: Is there any way to consider rest mass proportional to a time interval (from $t=0$ for example)? If so, one could transform $m_0 \cdot A$ using a Lorentz transformation. Otherwise there is no justification for such a procedure, we argue.

We suggest that m_0 may be proportional to the amount of time required to assemble it, one Δm_0 piece at a time. Thus:

M_0 is proportional to the amount of time required to assemble it with $M_0 = N \Delta m_0$, N being an integer ((4))

One may use $m_0 \cdot A$ in a Lorentz transformation in place of $c \cdot t$. In the moving frame, the $m_0 \cdot A/c$ time interval will have a spatial portion as well because the co-ordinate axes are moving. The question then becomes: What is A , assuming A is a constant, but m_0 transforms?

From special relativity, it is known that the quantity which transforms as the time component of 4-vector is:

$M_0 c$ ((5)) Thus $M_0 g(v) \cdot c$ represents a time interval and pc a spatial one.

Here $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. Thus: $x'/t'=v$ and $pc/(m_0 g c) = v$ as well. ((6))

$m_0 c$ is the object which represents a time interval in the rest frame (for a particle with rest mass). At this point, there is no concept of momentum or energy, just $m_0 c g(v)$ and $m_0 v c g(v)$. These are, however, not quantities used in interactions.

It is known that the $v \ll c$ limit is represent in Newtonian mechanics for which one has:

$P = mv$ ((7a)) and $KE = pp/2m_0$ ((7b)) as physical variables associated with interactions.

One may see that: $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $m_0 g(v) c$ are the expressions which become the required Newtonian variables in the $v \ll c$ limit. Thus, we have two sets of variables:

$m_0 c, 0$ which represents time, space and transforms to: $m_0 \gamma(v) c$ and $m_0 v \gamma(v) / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ ((8)) These allow one to use the Lorentz transformation.

On the other hand, one has physical interaction variables:

$$m_0 c, 0 \rightarrow E = m_0 \gamma(v) c^2, p = m_0 v \gamma(v) / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((9))$$

The 4-vector is (pc, E) and now if one wishes to write a $x'=vt'$ type of equation, one has:

$$1/E \cdot c/v = 1/p \text{ from } p = m_0 v \gamma(v) / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((10))$$

Thus, in the interaction picture (using interaction variables), time and space intervals associated with interactions are:

$$\text{constant}/E \text{ and } \text{constant}/p \quad (\text{where } \text{constant} = \hbar) \quad ((11))$$

The variables $m_0 c, 0$ or $m_0 \gamma(v) c$ and $m_0 v \gamma(v) / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$, on the other hand represent time and space intervals linked with $x'/t' = v$, i.e.

$$m_0 \gamma(v) c / (m_0 \gamma(v) v) = v. \quad ((12))$$

Such is not the case for p/E or $\text{constant}/p / \text{constant}/E$ for a particle with rest mass.

Thus, the ((12)) set of variables are used to justify a Lorentz transformation, but then identification of variables linked to interactions yields a different scenario, namely ((10)) and ((11)). We argue that ((11)) is linked with free particle quantum mechanics and physical interactions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Lorentz transformation is strictly a spacetime one. There is no reason to use $m_0 c$ as the 4-th component of a 4-vector unless it is equivalent to $c \cdot t$. We argue that one may consider $m_0 A$ (A is a constant) as representing the time interval required to create m_0 one delta m_0 at a time. It is like a frozen interval of time, but may therefore transform in a Lorentz transformation. In a moving frame, this will be associated with a distance $m_0 A \gamma(v)$ which is pc . Here $A = c$. These two variables are like $x'/t' = v$ i.e. $m_0 \gamma(v) c / (m_0 \gamma(v) v) = v$. Unfortunately $m_0 \gamma(v) c$ and $m_0 \gamma(v) v$ are not directly interaction variables. In Newtonian mechanics, one has the $v \ll c$ limit of these, i.e. $p = m_0 v$ and $KE = p^2/2m_0$ or $E = m_0 c^2 + p^2/2m_0$. If one insists on using the relativistic form of these interaction variables, then one has (for a particle with rest mass) : $1/E \cdot c/v = 1/p$ from $p = m_0 v \gamma(v) / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$. This is now a very different $W = \text{velocity unit variable} \cdot Y$ type of equation and leads to \hbar/E and \hbar/p as Δt and Δx intervals associated with interactions. Thus, one set of variables, $m_0 c, 0 \rightarrow m_0 \gamma(v) c, m_0 \gamma(v) v$ act as t, x variables and allow one to use the Lorentz transformation, but changing to interaction

variables, p and E , leads to a different $W = \text{velocity unit variable} * Y$ equation and different intervals, which we argue are physical intervals which apply to interactions, i.e. to free particle quantum mechanics.